

A new host record of *Thecaphora saponariae* (Ustilaginomycetes) from Dobrogea (Romania)

Cătălin Tănase¹ & Cvetomir M. Denchev^{2*}

¹Alexandru I. Cuza University of Iași, Faculty of Biology, 20 A Carol I Bd., RO-700505, Iași, Romania

²Institute of Botany, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 23 Acad. G. Bonchev St., 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria

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Abstract. *Silene thymifolia* is reported as a new host of *Thecaphora saponariae*.

Key words: Romania, smut fungi, *Thecaphora saponariae*

Silene thymifolia is a Pontic-Balkan element. It is recorded herein for the first time as a host of *Thecaphora saponariae*. The material was collected in Dobrogea (Romania).

Ustilospores from a dried specimen were examined under a light microscope after mounting in lactophenol solution, gently heating to the boiling point, and then cooling. The specimen is deposited in the herbarium I (Faculty of Biology Herbarium, Alexandru I. Cuza University of Iași).

Thecaphora saponariae (F. Rudolphi) Vánky, Mycotaxon 69: 94, 1998. — *Sorosporium saponariae* F. Rudolphi, Linnaea 4: 116, 1829.

Sori in the flowers, swollen, covered by the floral envelopes. **Spore mass** granular-powdery, light brown. **Spore balls** subglobose, ovoid, broadly ellipsoidal or irregular, composed of 10-60 ustilospores, at maturity disintegrating into small groups or separate ustilospores. **Ustilospores** subglobose to irregularly polyhedral or elongated, 12-21 × 10-15 (14.8±2.0 × 12.1±1.3) μm (*n* = 38), pale yellow to light yellowish brown; wall unequally thick, on the contact side *ca* 0.7 μm, finely verruculose, on the free side 1.5-2.5 (–3) μm thick, coarsely verruculose or irregularly wrinkled and incompletely reticulate (Fig. 1).

On *Silene thymifolia* Sibth. & Sm. **ROMANIA:** Dobrogea, distr. Constanța, Agigea, 44°06'32"N, 28°36'15"E, alt. *ca* 10 m, 10 Jul 2003, leg. C. Tănase (I 114 253).

Fig. 1. Ustilospores of *Thecaphora saponariae* on *Silene thymifolia* (I 114 253) in SEM

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*Corresponding author: e-mail: denchev@bio.bas.bg